

EDITORIAL

Era of Digital Impressions.

Impressions are considered to be an important aspect of prosthodontics. They have various applications, from fabricating casts or patient education to production of final or interim prosthesis. In the twenty first century where, artificial intelligence is slowly replacing conventional methods, digital impression systems are gaining popularity. The system uses a 3D camera to record the intra oral landmarks which are then processed by a computer to generate a virtual image. Digital impression systems provide us hassle-free treatment planning, patient communication, instructions to laboratories, a good amount of time is saved, which ultimately shortens the treatment schedules.

The digital impression technique has many other advantages, such as better acceptance by patients as there is no tray material. Dimensional changes of impression materials is not a factor using digital technology. The tooth preparation can be visualized in 3D and corrections can be made immediately.

The last few years has seen an increase in the number of optical intra oral scanners based on different technologies like triangulation, confocal, active wavefront sampling and stereophotogrammetry. Thus, a sound knowledge is required for clinicians to do an accurate treatment planning during the scanning of prepared teeth.

At present there is no scanning software, scanner, or system that can call itself flawless. More research work is needed specially in standardizing the procedures and in vivo studies. This state-of-the-art technology needs to be popularized by making the gadgets available and affordable. Also there must be nearby laboratories to accept the STL (Standard Tessellation Language) files and convert the virtual imaged to real 3D models.

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